

Figure S1. Distribution of significant trends ("discoveries") and non-significant pixels detected from annual mean EVI in Moroccan fir forests (Rif Mountains, Morocco) under the four analytical configurations: CMK (contextual Mann-Kendall test applied directly), PW-CMK (CMK applied to prewhitened time series), CMK-FDR (CMK with false discovery rate correction), and PW-CMK-FDR (prewhitened CMK with FDR correction). Significance thresholds were set at $\alpha = 0.10$ (uncorrected tests) and $q = 0.10$ (FDR-adjusted results).

Figure S2. Distribution of significant trends (“discoveries”) and non-significant pixels detected from annual mean EVI in Moroccan fir forests (Rif Mountains, Morocco) under the four analytical configurations: CMK (contextual Mann–Kendall test applied directly), PW-CMK (CMK applied to prewhitened time series), CMK-FDR (CMK with false discovery rate correction), and PW-CMK-FDR (prewhitened CMK with FDR correction). Significance thresholds were set at $\alpha = 0.01$ (uncorrected tests) and $q = 0.01$ (FDR-adjusted results).